

Fabrication of TiO₂ Nanowire Arrays Using Laser Interference Lithography Aided Hydrothermal Method

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Abstract - Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) is one of the most widely investigated semiconductor materials because of its unique properties. TiO₂ nanowire arrays can be synthesized through a two-step method, the fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) substrates were ablated using laser interference lithography technology, and TiO₂ nanowire arrays were grown on the patterned FTO substrates. The TiO₂ nanowire arrays were characterized by SEM and XRD measurements. This work provides a high efficient method for the fabrication of ordered TiO₂ nanowire arrays for different applications in highly functionalized assemblies and composites.

Keywords—*laser interference lithography; hydrothermal method; TiO₂ nanowire arrays*

I. INTRODUCTION

Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) is one of the most widely used semiconductor materials owing to its unique physical and chemical properties and many applications in medical treatment, environment purification and energy areas ranging from photocatalytic degradation and sensors to solar cells and lithium ion batteries.[1-7] Nanostructured TiO₂ shows unique properties because its quantum size effect, surface effect and macroscopic quantum tunneling effect. However, titanium dioxide faces several challenges, particularly, for the low recycling rate, high production costs.[8] Furthermore, the phase purity, morphology and structure of titanium dioxide have a constraint on its performance. Currently, although various forms of titanium dioxide have been prepared, especially in powder specimens, preparation of TiO₂ thin films with orientated growth properties still faces several challenges. Thus, preparing TiO₂ nanostructure films with the high specific surface area and oriented growth is deserving.

The various methods of synthesizing TiO₂ nanowire arrays developed to now include the sol-gel, sputtering method,[9, 10] hydrothermal method,[11] template synthesis method and electrochemical anodization method.[12-14] Among them, the sputtering method has higher requirements on the precision and scale of experimental equipment, and

the sol-gel method should strictly control the hydrolysis of reaction solution in the atmosphere. The advantage of the hydrothermal method is that purity, dispersion and crystallinity of nanocrystalline can be controlled by changing the synthesis conditions including the temperature and time of heating-up, the concentration of reaction solution.[15] During the past years, nanostructures, such as α -Fe₂O₃/graphene, ZrO₂ and TiO₂, fabricated by hydrothermal method, have been reported.[16-18]

Recent advances have revealed that highly ordered and well-aligned arrays of nanoparticles, the mechanical, electrical and optical properties, as well as surface chemistries, have been modified by the ordered systems. For instance, a new bifunctional α -Fe₂O₃ nanorods exhibit superior electroactivity and selectivity for the oxidation of nitrite and the reduction of hydrogen peroxide.[19] The large specific surfaces with aligned ZnO nanorods have been synthesized by an effective method.[20]

In this paper, FTO conductive glass with one- and two-dimensional grating structures was obtained by laser interference lithography. Highly ordered TiO₂ nanoclusters with nanoflower shape can be fabricated in the patterned FTO glass through a hydrothermal process. The laser technique has proven to be an effective and environment friendly approach in fabricating ordered TiO₂ nanoflowers. These one- and two-dimensional orientated nanoarrays demonstrate significant area enlargement on the surface, leading to higher photocatalytic efficiency. The method reported here can be extended to fabricate other semiconductor oxides and thus represents a critical avenue toward high-performance optoelectronics.

II. EXPERIMENT

In this experiment, a laser wavelength of 1064 nm was used for laser interference lithography. Before the experiment, the FTO (F:SnO₂, Tec 15, 10/0, Hartford Glass Company) samples were sonicated sequentially for 5 min by acetone, alcohol (Changchun Chemical Works) and deionized water and dried in the air. The laser beam was split

into two or three beams, the two or three beams were guided by high-reflective mirrors to interfere on the sample surface. The laser energy reached a threshold value of etching the FTO glass surface. The patterned FTO was washed three times with deionized water and then dried at room temperature. The one-dimensional or two-dimensional patterned FTO substrate was used for the following hydrothermal method.

In the hydrothermal reaction, 20 mL of deionized water and 20 mL of concentrated sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) were mixed to reach 40 mL volume. After the mixed solution was stirred for 10 min with a magnetic stirrer, 665 μL of titanium butoxide (TBT) was added while stirring, and continued stirring for another 10 min. The patterned FTO substrates were placed face-down with 45° degrees of the Teflon-lined. Subsequently, the hydrothermal reactor was placed in an electric oven for heating. After the hydrothermal synthesis, the hydrothermal reactor was rinsed with flowing water for 15 min.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 Two-beam and three-beam interference patterns were simulated using MATLAB when wavelength $\lambda = 1064$ nm.

Fig. 1 shows the two-beam and three-beam interference patterns simulated using MATLAB when the light wavelength $\lambda = 1064$ nm. Fig. 1a shows the simulated laser intensity distribution of the two-beam laser interference lithography. The two-beam interference pattern is a periodic and equidistant straight fringes, and the period equal to $\lambda/2\sin\theta$ where λ is the wavelength of the light, and θ is half the angle between the two beams. Fig. 1b shows the simulated laser intensity distribution of three-beam laser interference. The regions of bright red represent the highest laser intensity, the regions of dark blue represent the lowest intensity. The FTO conductive glass located at the highest laser intensity is “burned” and removed, while the FTO conductive glass surface at the lowest intensity remains unremoved.

Fig. 2 SEM images of ablated FTO substrate surfaces after direct laser interference ablation. (a), (c) 1D and 2D grating structures of top view, respectively, etched by two-beam and three-beam laser interference. (b), (d) Enlarged SEM images of 1D and 2D grating structures.

Fig. 2 shows the SEM images of patterned FTO substrate. Fig 2a and Fig 2c are 1D and 2D grating structures of top view, respectively, etched by two-beam and three-beam laser interference. Fig 2b and Fig 2d are high resolution SEM images of 1D and 2D grating structures.

The schematic of experimental setup is shown in Fig. 3. The 2D structures were obtained by three-beam laser interference lithography system. In the system, the laser beam was split into three beams by beam splitters. The incident and azimuthal angles of each beam were adjusted by beam splitters and mirrors. The quarter-wave plates and polarizers were used to select the polarization mode and control the energy. The patterned FTO substrate was used for hydrothermal reaction.

Fig. 3 Schematics of experimental setup.

Fig. 4 Unpatterned TiO₂ nanowire arrays.

The 1D structure was obtained by two-beam laser interference lithography system, which generated a pattern of grating with the period of $\lambda/2\sin\theta$ where λ =the wavelength of the light, and θ =half the angle between the two beams. The two beams passed through the half-wave plates and the polarizers. The laser energy was controlled by half wave plates, and the polarization angle was controlled by polarizers. The difference between 1D and 2D patterns is that the two-beam or three-beam laser interference is used in the process.

Fig. 5 (a) and (b) Top-view SEM images of 1D TiO₂ nanowire arrays. (c) and (d) Top-view SEM images of 2D TiO₂ nanowire arrays.

Fig. 4 shows the unpatterned TiO₂ nanowire arrays. Fig. 5a and Fig. 5b show the top view SEM images with different magnifications of 1D grating patterned TiO₂ nanowire arrays achieved according to the two-step process. It can be clearly observed from SEM image in Fig. 5b that the morphology of TiO₂ nanowire arrays are flower clusters. Thus, the

Fig. 6 (a) Cross-sectional SEM images of the TiO₂ nanowire arrays. (b) XRD pattern of TiO₂ nanowire arrays on the FTO substrate.

fabricated TiO₂ nanowire arrays are described as 1D TiO₂. Fig. 5c and Fig. 5d show the SEM image of the 2D grating patterned TiO₂ (2D TiO₂ for short) achieved by three-beam laser interference followed by hydrothermal method. Fig. 5c and Fig. 5d show that the TiO₂ nanowire arrays are grown according to the 2D grating structure on the FTO. The growth of the TiO₂ nanowire arrays fully complies with the beam dot pattern. It clearly shows that the TiO₂ array is very neat with a structure of flower clusters. Fig. 6a shows the cross-sectional SEM image of TiO₂ nanowire arrays. The TiO₂ nanowires were found with an average diameter of 300 nm and the length of 6 μm. Fig. 6b shows the X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern of TiO₂ nanowire arrays. The TiO₂ nanowire arrays show significant (101) and (004) diffraction peaks, which match with the pure anatase phase of TiO₂ (JCPDS 211272).

Fig. 7 The length and diameter of TiO₂ nanowires were fabricated with different times and different temperatures.

Fig. 7 shows the change in the length and diameter of the TiO₂ nanowires fabricated with different times and different temperatures. Fig. 7a and Fig 7b show the changes in the length and diameter of the TiO₂ nanowires when the heating time is different at 150°C. As shown in Fig. 7a, when the heating time is 4h for the hydrothermal method. The length of TiO₂ nanowires is 3μm. As the time increases, the length of TiO₂ nanowires reaches 13μm when the heating time is 16h. When the heating time is in the range of 4-16h, the length of the TiO₂ nanowires show a continuous increase. The diameter of TiO₂ nanowires reaches 300 nm when the

heating time is 8h. Despite the increase in temperature, the length of the TiO₂ nanowires will not increase. Fig. 7c and Fig. 7d show the changes in the length and diameter of the TiO₂ nanowires when the heating temperature is different at 8h. As shown in Fig. 7c, when the heating temperature is 100°C for the hydrothermal method, the length of the TiO₂ nanowires is 1μm. As the heating temperature increases, the length of the TiO₂ nanowires reaches 6μm when the heating temperature is 175°C. When the heating temperature is in the range of 100-175°C, the length of the TiO₂ nanowire shows a continuous increase. The diameter of TiO₂ nanowire reaches a maximum value of 300 nm at 150 °C and remains unchanged even though the heating temperature increase again.

IV. CONCLUSION

In summary, highly ordered TiO₂ nanowire arrays were fabricated using a simple two-step process, the patterned FTO conductive glass can be obtained with one- and two-dimensional grating structures by laser interference lithography and then the TiO₂ nanowire arrays exhibiting nanoflower shape were prepared through a hydrothermal process. The periodicity of the grating and the size of TiO₂ nanowire arrays can be precisely controlled by changing the parameters of laser beams and hydrothermal conditions. It is a useful approach to create patterned nanostructures for applications such as medical treatment, environment purification and energy areas.

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